

A growing global wheat crisis: securing current & future supply

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The war in Ukraine has negatively impacted the lives of Ukrainian citizens as well as the livelihoods of nations and people around the world. Shelled fields, seizure or damage to agricultural property and compromise of port infrastructure in Ukraine have destroyed crops, prevented spring planting and are likely to have a major impact on the harvest of 6 million hectares of wheat planted in farmers' fields across Ukraine. This effects the downstream availability of wheat within Ukraine as well as onward into the global wheat export market.

The ability of countries to buy wheat from major exporters like Russia and the Ukraine (together representing 28.6% of the wheat traded worldwide in 2018-19, see Figure 1) at low relative cost over many years has resulted in growing import-dependence and reduced production in many regions (**Figure 1**). For example, in East Africa local production has been disincentivized by easy global trade and low prices leading to low levels of production even in areas with favorable biophysical characteristics for wheat production. The concentration of exports and reliance on low-cost imports for a major staple grain places significant vulnerabilities on the global food system. Over the past two decades, the world has witnessed multiple crisis erupt over the social and political instability caused by rising costs for staple cereals.

Today we see high levels of price volatility in global wheat markets. We have previously highlighted that reduced supply and increasing prices are likely to have the biggest impacts on vulnerable communities in the Global South (<https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-022-00789-x>). Mitigating these effects requires co-ordinated short-, medium- and long-term actions as we have described in detail, drawing on the wealth of technical expertise in the international agricultural and development community (<https://zenodo.org/record/6380085#.YovpU3bMKUk>).

In the short-term, the effects of reduced wheat supply need to be addressed through prioritizing production (particularly in existing highly productivity wheat producing regions), applying market interventions to target wheat grain for human consumption (discouraging its use as livestock feed and for the production of bioethanol) and the use of flour substitution. In the medium-term the community needs to urgently address the resilience of supply through expansion of wheat area into areas of biophysical potential (within the agroecological and policy framework of a country and/or region), development of import substitution pathways and plans and packages of technical support drawing on the latest developments in the global wheat community (encompassing upstream research, breeding improved varieties and integrated agronomy) and the mainstreaming of satellite earth observation for real-time assessment and analysis of threats. For the longer-term we envisage a global community integrating research and development around the maintenance of productivity within the diversity of agroecosystems, programs and interventions designed to stimulate gender empowerment and safeguard ecological integrity in rural communities and sustain investment in the science of agriculture, including supportive agricultural policies.

Over three months we have seen a regional conflict have major global impacts on wheat, an essential food security staple. The length of the current crisis is unpredictable, although even at its current duration it serves to highlight the interconnectedness of the wheat trade. Together with recent real time climate impacts reducing yields in South Asia (<https://www.cimmyt.org/blogs/wheat-versus-heat/>) this highlights the inherent fragility of global wheat supply. The global wheat community should urgently align to develop, test, and deploy applied solutions for safeguarding future wheat security.

Figure 1. More than three quarters of the global wheat trade (78.8% in 2018 and 2019) is dominated by just seven producer countries (Russia, USA, Argentina, Canada, Ukraine, Australia, and France). Before the conflict, Russia and Ukraine represented more than a quarter (28.8% in 2018 and 2019) of the global wheat export (source: FAOSTAT). All data and code available here: <https://github.com/FBaudron/Newsletter> Bentley Baudron Figure